

AN EVALUATION OF THE CRITICAL CAUSATIVE FACTORS OF ETHNO-RELIGIOUS CONFLICTS USING THEMATIC NETWORK ANALYSIS IN BAUCHI TOWN, BAUCHI STATE, NIGERIA.

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Abstract

The history of Nigeria as a nation state is bedeviled with occurrences of violent ethno-religious conflicts especially in the northern region. In Bauchi particularly, hardly a year pass without recording one form of ethno-religious conflict or another. This study seeks to evaluate the Critical Causative Factors of these incessant Ethno-Religious Conflicts in Bauchi, Bauchi state, Nigeria. The study targeted residents of Bauchi town; leaders of the different ethnic and religious groups; peace and conflict resolution organisations in the area; the State Ministry of Justice, and the Ministry of Religious Affairs. Twelve key informants were purposively selected for the study and interviewed. A total of four focused group discussion were conducted. The qualitative data gathered were analysed using thematic network analysis where the researcher develops appropriate codes in accordance with the study objective. Main goodness of fit indices was used to evaluate the validity of measurement and structural models. The study identified twenty-two (22) themes as causative factors of ethno religious conflict in the research area. Main out of which includes: unemployment, infrastructure deficit, safety and security, lack of education, poor business investment, as well as government policy were found to be the critical causative factors in the research domain. To resolve the problem under review is to address the highlighted critical causative factors within the research by all concerned.

Keywords: analysis, conflict, evaluation, ethnicity, factors and religion.

Introduction

Religion is sociologically argued to be a socio-cultural system of designated behaviors and practices, morals, world views, texts, sanctified places, prophecies, ethics or organizations that relates humanity to supernatural elements. Religion is therefore value-based which make its adherents emotionally attached to it with little or no tolerance of anything against it. Other scholars define religion as a belief by a group of people that they consider as pure. It is a cultural institution and an instrument and means of satisfying needs. It is also a belief system that is emotionally charged (Oтите & Ogonwo, 2009; Shabiand, 2001).

On the other hand, Osaghae (1998) defines ethnicity as a social formation that is guided by specific cultural practices as well as unique symbols. Individuals in these groups are considered to have common affinity separating them from others. Ethnicity simply refers to those attitudes, prejudices and beliefs which members of an ethnic community hold about themselves and use in identifying or differentiating others. It involves the discrimination by members of one ethnic group against others due to diverse socio-cultural values. Religion and ethnicity are the identifying variables in the examination of the conflict under review.

The Study Area

Bauchi state has a total of 49,259.01km land area, which represents about 5.3% of Nigeria total land mass. The state is located between latitude 9°31' and 12°31' north of the equator.

Longitudinally, it lies between longitudes 8°51' and 11°0' east of Greenwich meridian. The state is bordered by seven other states of the federation: Kano and Jigawa to the north, Taraba to the south, Gombe and Yobe to the East and Kaduna to the west. Of the [36 states](#) of Nigeria, Bauchi is the [fifth largest in area](#) and [seventh most populous](#) with an estimated population of over 6,530,000 as of 2016 census. The state is divided between the [West Sudanian savanna](#) in the south and the drier, [semi-desert Sahelian savanna](#) in the north with a small part of the montane [Jos Plateau](#) in the southwest. A key defining characteristic of the state's landscape is [Yankari National Park](#), a large wildlife park in southern Bauchi State. Bauchi State has been inhabited for years by various ethnic groups, including the [Bolewa](#), Butawa, [Warji](#), the [Fulani](#), [Kanuri](#), [Karai-Karai](#), Fulani, [Gerawa](#); the [Zaar \(Sayawa\)](#), Ngas and [Jarawa](#) among others. Religiously, the vast majority of the state's population (85%) are [Muslim](#) with smaller [Christian](#) and [traditionalist](#) minorities at about 6% and 9%, respectively.

Bauchi State Development Update (2005) Vol.2

In the early 1800s, the [Fulani jihad](#) seized much of modern-day Bauchi State and formed the [Bauchi Emirate](#) under the [Sokoto Caliphate](#). About 90 years later, a British expedition occupied the Emirate and incorporated it as Bauchi Province into the [Northern Nigeria Protectorate](#) which later merged into [British Nigeria](#) before becoming independent as [Nigeria](#) in 1960. Originally, modern-day Bauchi State was a part of the post-independence [Northern Region](#) until 1967 when the region was split and the area became part of the [North-Eastern State](#). After the North-Eastern State was split, Bauchi State was formed on 3rd February 1976.

As a major agriculture-based state, the State economy partially relies on livestock and crops, such as [cotton](#), [groundnuts](#), [millet](#), [tomatoes](#), and [yams](#) with advanced irrigation schemes increasing agricultural production since statehood. Other industries include food processing and canning facilities, [tin](#) and [columbite](#) mining, and tourism in [Yankari National park](#) and its WikkiwarmSprings.

Fig. A1: Map of Bauchi local government showing the major ethnic group and religious compositions of the study area

Source: *Bauchi State Development Update (2005) Vol.2*

Theoretical framework

Violent human conflict is one of the most complex social phenomena that human beings experience. In such conflict, especially those involving ethno-religious groups, participants often have deep convictions concerning contested geographies, historical narratives, moral grievances, religious values, or sometimes even competing cosmologies and gods. Such complex social organizations in collision create significant dilemmas for any researcher attempting to understand their full scope and significance. This does not mean that the pursuit of understanding social conflicts

is eclectic or improvised. On the contrary, this is an extremely complex phenomenon that no single method, or single approach can claim to have a monopoly on the truth, especially when the “truths” of the conflict are in deadly competition.

Conflict theory as propounded by in the works of Karl Marx and Max Weber is adopted for the purposes of this study. Marxist and Weberian conflict theories tend to disagree over the precise basis on which society is divided into different groups, and the exact nature of the conflict that results from these divisions (Haralambos and Holborn 2004). This work departs from Karl Marx to Weber's explanation of conflict because; Weber has more all-encompassing explanation to the recurrent ethno-religious conflicts in Bauchi state. Weber rejected Karl Marx's view that the division between the owners and non-owners of property was the only significant division between groups in society. He argued that there could be numerous divisions within the two basic classes, depending upon the market situation of individuals (Weber 1947). Division between groups in societies could also be predicated on status, political interests as well as their economic position. Weber's view on classes, status, group and parties reflects the main themes of conflict theory. To Weber, social structure consists of many different groups, and these groups have different interests, these interests are not just economic. The incessant ethno-religious conflicts in Bauchi seem to revolve around status, economic, culture and power. A particular group might strive for greater prestige or status rather than economic power, while another group strives for political domination and others for greater religious domination and territorial expansion.

In light of the above complexity of groups and group interests, the Weberian conflict theory perfectly explains the ethno-religious conflicts in Bauchi, Bauchi state Nigeria. Applying this theoretical framework to explain ethno-religious conflict in the study area, indicated that Nigerian society generally, since its formation is deeply complex and pluralistic. It is this complexity and pluralistic nature of Bauchi state that made the struggle for recourses (land and power) in the metropolis, a do or die affairs.

Weber's Conflict theory points out that the diversity in groups and interests are likely to lead to different ideologies, reflecting their position and the condition of their lives. Conflict theory therefore spend time focusing on how this leads to revolution and dichotomies. From a more radical approach in the analysis of ethnicity and ethnic antagonism, three basic conditions must be presented which can facilitate inter and or intra ethno-religious conflict:

- Identifiable groups
- Competition for resources
- Unequal power

From the religious perspective, one observes that there is the pluralism of religion. However, it is generally acknowledged that Islam dominates the human landscape of Bauchi. But in recent times, this dominance has been threatened by its brother foreign religion (Christianity).

There is a diversity of opinion about the sources, dimensions and consequences of the conflicts. But most scholars agree that the causes of conflict can be reduced to three broad classifications namely; resource driven conflict, conflict over values and those over psychological needs (Best, 2004). These three factors appeared prevalent in the intermittent ethno-religious conflicts in Bauchi, Bauchi state, Nigeria.

The concept of Conflict

The term conflict is derived from the Latin word 'Confligare' which means to strike together. This could be likened to the spark witnessed whenever we strike a match box with a match stick to produce fire and heat; hence heat is one of the most common metaphors used to describe a conflict (Ayuba, 2016). In psychology theories of personality, conflict is a state of discomfort or stress caused by an individual experiencing two or more desires or needs that are incompatible (Grigg, 2006). Consequently, Conflict connotes “opposition among social entities directed against one another”

(Wright, 1990). Kriesberg (1973) conceives conflict as “a relationship between two parties or more who believe they have two incompatible goals”. Similarly, Coser defines conflict as “an incompatible behavior between parties whose interests are, or appear to be incompatible or clashing”. Bagaji (2012) sees conflict as a state of disharmony and tension in an interactional process where two or more opinions, perspectives, and values contradict each other. A common denominator which runs through the various definitions is disagreement or argument, whether among people, groups, and countries or even within an individual.

Ethno-religious conflicts: A Global Over-view

Ethno-religious conflicts are conflicts among groups where religion is an integral part of the social and cultural life, and religious institutions among these groups possess moral legitimacy and mobilization potential (Kadayifci-Orellana, 2009). These conflicts, according to Ugwu (2011), are generated on the basis of real or imagined “differences” rooted in ethnic and religious identities. Ethno-religious conflict is a global problem. In Europe, instances of ethno-religious conflicts have been experienced in countries such as France where between 2005 and 2007 there were cases of ethno-religious conflicts between the French natives and the Muslim immigrants mostly of Arabian extraction (Meier & Hawes, 2009). In 2005 particularly, the conflict led to thousands of vehicles being torched, many people reported death, some injured, and hundreds of millions of dollars' worth of damage recorded (Ibid). In Northern Ireland, from 1969 to 1999, almost 3,500 people died as a result of conflict between 'British' Protestants and 'Irish' Catholics. In Asia, ethno-religious conflict has also been witnessed between the Israeli Jewish and Palestinian Muslims that has seen loss of thousands of lives, repression, intimidation and violence (Perry, 2015).

Asia has also witnessed and continues to experience ethno-religious conflicts. Hindu India and Muslim Pakistan had a conflict that left about half a million people dead. The conflict between India and Pakistan, currently independent states, continues to date, with the contestation of Kashmir area being the area each lays claim; claims that are still founded on their religious differences and their history (Brunt, 2016). In Iraq, Christians, Shia's, Shabaks, Turkmen and Yazidis among other minority groups are facing a range of conflicts including mass killings, looting of property and destruction of religious sites on the grounds of their religion and ethnicity by the Sunni (OHCHR, 2014).

Several countries in Africa have also been affected by ethno-religious conflicts. Sudan, for example, has been faced with conflict between the Northern Arab Muslims and the Christian South people dominated by the Dinka and the Nuer; a conflict that resulted in the formation of South Sudan as a nation state. In the conflict, no fewer than 50,000 people were killed, more than 2.3 million rendered homeless, and schools shut down (Berkley Center for Religion, Peace & World Studies, 2013). In the Central Africa Republic, there has been conflict between the Muslim Seleka and Christian anti-Balaka that has led to numerous losses of lives, mutilations, loss of property, and mass displacements.

Nigeria has been confronted by ethno-religious conflicts since its amalgamation in 1914 by the British colonialists; between, among and within ethnic groups in the north and south, and between Muslims and Christians (Ugorji, 2016). From 1967 to 1970, Nigeria was ravaged by a bloody civil war that occurred between the Muslim north (mainly the Hausa-Fulani people) and the Christian south (mainly the Igbo people), resulting to the death of over a million people (Ugorji, 2016). Further violent conflicts between ethno-religious groups of the north and south were experienced in the 1980s through to the early periods of the 2000s (Maitatsine, Tiv-Jukun, Tiv-Fulani, Ishekiri-Ibibio, Ife-Modakeke etc.). Recently, the emergence of Boko Haram terrorist group and the surge in its attacks have reignited the old debate of what it means for Muslims and Christians, Igbos, Hausa-Fulanis, Yorubas and the other ethnic minorities in the country to coexist and live together harmoniously.

In Bauchi state particularly, there have been numerous cases of ethno-religious conflicts. In 1991, 1995 and 2001, there were violent conflicts between Hausa-Fulani-Muslim and Sayawa

Christians. These conflicts claimed hundreds of lives, rendered thousand homeless, led to loss of millions of Naira worth of property. In 2011, following the announcement of the Presidential election results, there were violent ethno-religious conflicts between Hausa-Fulani Muslims and southern Christian communities living in the North (mainly the Igbos) and other Christian minorities of the north that led to loss of lives, left thousands homeless or displaced and caused destruction of property (Eme et al, 2012). Other instances of ethno-religious conflicts in Bauchi include the November 2002 Miss World Religious riot in Bauchi, the February 2006 Danish Cartoon Protest, the April 2006 Government Day Secondary School Army Barracks, Bauchi conflict, the 2007 Government Day Secondary School Yelwa, conflict, the 2008 Hausa-Sayawa conflict in Yelwa, the 2009 Dutsen-Tanishi Boko-Haram attack, the 2010 Muslim-Christian conflict of Federal low-cost extension, the March 2011 Kala-Kato conflict in Zango and the 2021 Hausa-Muslim vs Sayawa-Christian conflict in Gudum area of Bauchi. Wunti (2016), Jega (2002), Omotola (2009), and Salawu (2010) observed that, there is thin line between religious and ethnic conflicts. It is therefore, common to find a person categorizing a conflict as either religious or ethnic. It is also, important to note that, most conflicts start as religious conflict and end up as ethnic conflicts and vice-versa, hence constituting ethno-religious conflicts.

Some Causes and Consequences of Ethno-Religious Conflicts

Madu& Ibrahim (2013) noted that in Nigeria, allegation of nepotism and bigotry, marginalization, discrimination, victimization, exploitation, domination, oppressions, and neglect are the main triggers of ethno-religious conflicts. There is no agreement among groups and individuals on how status, power, and wealth should be shared because of competitive interests. Other studies found that when deprived groups (ethno-religious groups) attempt to be powerful and gain more wealth to increase their dominant ideology, beliefs, norms, and values. Occurrence of Conflicts becomes mainly inevitable as with the case of Zangon-Kataf riots of 1992, Wukari 2010, and Boko Haram (Adebayo, 2010; Abdulkadir, 2011). Scholars also acknowledge fanaticism, overzealous religious leaders, politicizing of religious activities, injustice, ignorance, and poverty as responsible factors for ethno-religious conflict in Nigeria (Aleyomi, 2012; Madu& Ibrahim, 2013).

Halliru (2012) revealed that political leaders in Bauchi state and other states in Nigeria have failed to promote economic progress, forge national integration, and establish good governance through deliberate policies leading to mass unemployment and poverty; hence class, religious, ethnic, and repeated communal conflicts. Otite (1990) argues that most of the ethno-religious conflicts in Nigeria are caused by scarce political and economic resources; land space and resource competition; disregard for cultural symbols; and population explosion.

Gofwen (2004) observe that religious intolerance is a major source of ethno-religious conflict with attendant destructive tendencies in all societies since the existence of mankind. Even though the causes of ethno-religious conflict may be different as explained by different authors, they all emphasize on governance, economic, and socio-political factors as the main cause of ethno-religious conflicts. In recent years, the emergence of Boko Haram has led to a large scale of unimaginable loss of human lives and property. They carry out bomb attacks and raids to groups that they consider "religiously others." There are similar characteristics between the Boko Haram and Maitatsine as far as armed resistance, organizational planning, objectives, and philosophy are concerned. Salawu (2010) contends that the forceful introduction of Islamic laws in states with diverse population has ignited ethno-religious conflicts in northern parts of Nigeria.

Consequences of these ethno-religious conflicts, often include loss of lives; displacement of people; destruction of property, infrastructure and development projects. It also threatened national security; disrupt school activities; create psychological trauma; generate unemployment and economic decline (Ugorji, 2016; Egwu, 2017). The conflict derails national integration manifested by the disunity, hatred and insecurity and marginalization (Adedayo, 2015; Danjibo, 2014).

Curbing Ethno-religious Conflicts

Empirical data reveal that ethno-religious conflicts affect the social and physical arrangement of people to places they consider safer. They are forced to settle along ethnic and religious divides that they subscribe to as is the case with most cities in Northern Nigeria. As a consequence, there is a negative impact on the use of land and governance (administration). Studies suggest that, government ought to checkmate persistent ethno-religious conflict and ensure that people adhere to land use and planning regulations (Omirin & Gambo, 2012; Halliru, 2012). Even though all the religions teach tolerance, forgiveness, acceptance, love and peace most followers ignore these fundamental tenants and ignorantly consider anyone who might hold a different opinion or not in their norm of belief as an enemy. In today's world we get discriminated every day for the choice of religion, values, morals, culture, and depending on ethnic grouping of a person. "Prejudice afflicts us in two ways. prejudice about something that obstructs our ability to deal with the specific matters, and the persons to which it applies in the best possible way" (Halliru, 2012).

Aleyomi (2012), recommends that there is need for grassroots education targeting young people who are vulnerable when it comes to recruitment by extremist groups. This process is gradual but, will help disabuse the mentality that Nigeria is a secular country which may lead to downplay of morality. Abdulkadir (2011) was concerned with strengthening of government agencies and institutions for easy and efficient address of grievances. Absorbing youth, the Nigeria Council of Women Society (NCWS), National Youth Council, Political Parties, the National Institute for Policy and Strategic Studies (NIPSS), the National Youth Service Corps (NYSC), and the National Orientation Agency (NOA) among others in various assignments will foster unity and help in building the nation for sustainable development.

Studies on conflict management agree that both the local, states and federal governments should encourage functional and effective platforms for leaders from diverse ethno-religious groups to design network that can be used to prevent and or manage conflicts efficiently. It is important to note that in most parts of the country, especially the North; ethnic, traditional, religious, and even political leaders hardly engage in discussion on ethno-religious conflict; thereby compounding the precarious condition. (Lukpata & Dada, Abdulkadir, 2011; 2016; Aleyomi, 2012).

Religion and Conflict Management

Religion has been viewed as an important instrument for conflict management and its resolution. Therefore, it is used to encourage peaceful coexistence among warring parties could help greatly in ironing out some of the greatest challenges associated with ethno-religious conflict in Bauchi state Nigeria. There has been an argument advanced by some people that, the use of religion as an instrument of conflict resolution and peace-building in contemporary times has improved relationships between people of different faiths. Nigeria as one of the theatres of ethno-religious conflict in Africa has found inter-religious or inter-faith approaches to conflict management as comprehensive and insightful. This is due to its capacity building opportunities that substantially help creating greater sense of sustainable peace among followers of Islam and Christianity in the country. The approach has elevated an effort by concerned religious leaders and other actors mostly peace professionals and volunteers from NGOs to foster peace via teaching of religious scriptures. It was on this premise that, His Eminence, Alhaji Muhammad Sa'ad Abubakar, the Sultan of Sokoto and President-General, Nigeria Supreme Council for Islamic Affairs (NSCIA) states;

..."I have seen how people of goodwill could make a world of difference, how the right word at the appropriate time could heal an old wound; how a little help to those in distress could rekindle hope in our common humanity and how people of virtue, courage and determination could set aside their fears and misgivings to work together to re-establish and strengthen the bases of mutual coexistence within their diverse communities...."

The trend is increasingly gaining ground in the Northern region by motivating individuals and

groups to become active in an attempt to manage conflict and ensure peaceful coexistence. The involvement of individuals and NGOs has fostered post conflict reconciliation and interfaith mediation in various parts of Northern Region, Nigeria and Africa at large. This is a new development that witnessed increasing acceptability among followers of the two major religions in Nigeria. Interfaith action in Nigeria is considered to be popular means of dealing with conflict that even transcend conflict resolution since it demonstrated its impact on the life of the common man. The interreligious peacemakers are thought to be good in ensuring relations between groups in conflict situation are improved and invariably change as well. Therefore, religion's role in helping to avert conflicts and also building peace is crucial component in helping to achieve human development.

Methodology

Key informant interviews (KII) were conducted with 12 suitably qualified leaders of the different ethnic and religious groups, two each from the six locations of the study covering representatives of Christian Muslim peace forum, Bauchi state peace forum, representative of the Christian association of Nigeria (CAN), Jama'atunasil Islam (JNI), representatives of Bauchi State Ministry of Justice and the Ministry of Religious Affairs. The study also conducted 4 focus group discussions (FGD) to help elicit responses that were otherwise not revealed from the KII. Data was analysed using thematic network analysis with appropriate codes developed in accordance with the study objectives. Main goodness of fit indices like the Absolute Fit Index, Parsimonious Fit Index and Incremental Index were used to evaluate the validity of measurement and structural models.

The Structure of Thematic Network Analysis

The process of thematic networks was not targeted to realize an argument or the end of justifications; rather it provides a method for breaking up text, and findings within its explicit justifications. The three classes of themes are:

Thematic Network Analysis

Thematic analysis is a search for themes that emerge as being important to the description of the phenomenon (Daly et al., 1997). Thematic analysis can either identify the themes pertaining to a particular research question (deductive analysis) or it can identify themes that are observed across the entire data range (inductive analysis) (Braun & Clark, 2006).

Stages of Data Coding

The stages of data coding on the chart are shown in Figure 1 on the following page which represents each stage of coding process.

Figure 1; Diagrammatic representation of the Stages Undertaken to code the data (Adopted from Boyatzis, 1998; Crabtree & Miller, 1999)

Stage 1: Developing the code manual

In this study, the template developed was based on six broad code categories which formed the code manual (motives, social relationships, the meaning of social action, systems of relevance, ideal types,

and common sense). The template clearly demonstrates how the fundamental process of communication between a source and recipient of feedback is underpinned by a more complex process of interpretation in relation to assessing feedback credibility. For this study, codes were written with reference to Boyatzis (1998) and identified by:

- i. The code name,
- ii. The description of the concerned theme, and
- iii. An explanation of how the theme occurs.

Stage 2: Testing the reliability of the code

Following the coding process of the documents using the predefined codes, the codes formulated were reviewed and ascertained.

Stage 3: Summarizing data and identifying initial themes

This process involves reviewing and summarizing the raw data. This procedure was first used to analyze transcript of the interview and focus group discussion.

Stage 4: Applying template of codes and additional coding

The codes were developed using the manual and entered as nodes while they were matched with the coded segments of data selected as representative of the code.

Stage 5: Connecting the codes and identifying themes

The process of linking the identified themes and the codes across the two sets of data, grouped under captions that directly relate to the research questions.

Stage 6: Corroborating and legitimating coded themes

The final stage demonstrates the procedure for grouping the themes that were previously identified from the coded text.

Discussion and Implication

Figure 2: Thematic Network Analysis to identify factors Triggering Ethno-Religious Crisis in Bauchi (Interview Survey, 2019).

Theme 1: Socio-economic Development

At the individual level socioeconomic development stands for such activities that transforms an individual's capabilities or potentials which build human capital and enhance employability and support quality of life and also facilitate the achievement of one's dreams and aspirations. Societal level, socioeconomic development refers to the capacity of the people in a given society to deal with

the environment base on good understanding of nature (science) and reasonable application of the understanding of nature into practice (technology) and on the manner on which work is organized. Rodney 1972.

The response from the interviewees was that socio-economic development is affected by ethno-religious conflict. According to the interviewees, socio-economic issues are part of the reasons why these conflicts occur. When youth are living in abject poverty, societal marginalization, they may decide to do whatever that comes to their mind or to do whatever they think will help them to earn a living. Furthermore, they mentioned that, as human beings we have basic needs that are indispensable, which have to be addressed especially as one cannot satisfy one's basic needs, and that the government cannot provide water, health facilities, schools, roads and other basic needs, are factors that will affect society adversely. Thus, whenever there is a conflict you see the youth are participating in order to vandalize people's shops and houses to loot their property but if they are self-sufficient, they may not participate let alone steal something from somebody's property. So, poor socio-economic stand is also one of the reasons behind ethno-religious crises in Bauchi.

Unemployment can also hamper socioeconomic development. The first respondent interviewed on the issue of unemployment lamented that unemployment contributed to the conflict. "When somebody doesn't have anything to do, he will be ready to comply or to engage himself in whatever thing that come to his mind. He's vulnerable to all these devilish and evil forces, anything that comes to his mind will easily be (you know) patronize by such person especially the youth". In addition, another interviewee stated that, unemployment is a big issue, as you see now, we have number of youths that are not in school and in the other side they are not employed in either public or private sectors. So, whenever there is a problem, either political or religious crisis or may be a border conflict, these youths are the ones, that are active participant in the conflicts; but if they are employed non will come and participate in crisis because is risking one's life. Employed youth are responsible in the community. When they are bound to a family, they don't participate in such unfortunate events.

Some respondents also stated that Lack of education is the first factor in ethno-religious conflicts. Lack of education, that's ignorance. This is part of the major problem of ethno-religious conflict. So, there is need for every Muslim and a Christian to know the teachings of their religions. For example, Islam is not only concerned about the religious practices, its concern about both the religious practice and the relationship that is 'Mu'amalat' how to relate with people. It's also an 'Ibadat' that is worship, if you practice it according to the teaching of the religion but ignorant you know some people are too extremists, once you have a different religion with someone, so you don't greet him, you don't relate with them, you don't (do) anything with them. So that is caused by ignorance, which is a major factor behind such disagreement or conflict.

Many respondents mentioned that poor investment in the study area has exacerbated different ethno-religious conflicts. Investments is relatively associated with job creation and wealth distribution. The youth felt they were marginalised to some extent. So they tend to be violent on issues that can be easily and amicably resolved.

Theme 2: Infrastructure

The respondents explained that infrastructural development is something that will help the government agents and agencies, the society itself to ensure the protection of lives and property. So, when the infrastructures are inadequate, government agents and agencies, members of the society may be helpless in containing some of these conflicts or some of the things that causes or lead to the conflicts.

Theme: Socio-religious

The issue of socio-religion as it relates to lack of safety and security or insecurity is one of the things that lead some youth to think of ways to defend themselves against whatever attack because to

them the security provision is not adequate to protect for their lives and property. Such also helps in promoting ethno-religious crisis. Respondents mentioned that, when they say safety, they mean as a citizen, you are entitled to safety, the government need to provide security for you, but at times, even during the conflict, when securities are deployed at times some of them tend to (ahh) exceed their limit while trying to ensure or restore peace. Some of them has malignant intention (they have selfish interest). For example, when there is a conflict in an area dominated by a particular religion, such as, Muslims or Christian like in Yelwa area, so when there is a conflict between them or when it is a religious disagreement between Muslim and Christian, so when security Forces are deployed to that area some of them will try to help their fellow brothers. The interviewer then asked: So, are you saying even the Security forces takes side on ethno-religious conflict? Yes.

Some respondents stated that Government policy has its merits and demerits. They posited that “Government policy is the issue of good governance, if there is no good governance anything can happen in the society forget about the issue of unemployment, forget about the issue of whether one is educated or not. So, in respect to government policy, as said, the government has obligation to provide the social amenities to the society and if the government cannot provide the social amenities as mentioned earlier: such as portable drinking water, schools, hospitals, good roads networks and all that is needed. These are obligation on the government and if the government cannot provide that factor could cause security challenges. So, these are some of the factors behind or wherever there is conflict you see that these factors are responsible for making the situation to become bad. On the possible solution, if the contributing factors to the religious conflict can be made to be what they are supposed to be; that can be the solution to all these (crises)? Yes. If you want to solve a problem, you have to know the cause. It's like going to a doctor telling him your problem, if you say you have headache, the doctor will not say go and take Panadol Extra, he will try to find out the cause of the headache. It is a sign and symptom of another problem. If he detected is hunger, the doctor will tell you to go and eat and if you are tired, the doctor will tell you to go and sleep. Solution depends on the actual cause of the actual problem.

Validation of Triggers of Ethno-Religious Crisis Using Focus Group Discussion (FGD)

This section focuses on validation of triggers of ethno-religious crisis through FGD. The participants of the focus group discussion identify factors triggering ethno-religious conflicts as components which will provide the basis for carrying out data collection using KII.

Purpose of the Focus Group

The study conducted 4FGD with different but homogeneous groups of one multi ethnic women Muslim, one multi ethnic women Christians, one multi ethnic Muslim Men and one Multi ethnic Christian Men with competent participants drawn from the six locations of the study in Bauchi local government area, Bauchi state, Nigeria. This step is taken in order to achieve the study objective which is to identify the critical causative factors triggering ethno-religious conflicts in Bauchi, Bauchi State Nigeria.

Conclusion

In every multi-ethnic and multi-religious country, occasional conflicts are bound to occur and Nigeria is not an exception. The phenomena should rather be considered as a challenge that requires maturity, courage, understanding and sincerity of purpose from all parties involved for it to be resolved. Indeed, there is more that unite all humans irrespective of religion and ethnicity than that which divide them.

The primary objective of every government is to protect lives and properties of its people by all legitimate means possible, however these objectives cannot be achieved in an environment full of discontent and animosities. It is therefore the responsibility of government to put in place a mechanism

where people from all background will fill safe, secure and invulnerable. This can be done through collaborative effort with religious leaders, opinion molders, youth as well as community leaders. At the moment findings of the study suggests that all these crucial relationships are at their lowest eve, hence the recurrent incidences of ethno-religious conflicts in the study area.

Recommendations

- i. Government should focus on the provision of employment opportunities for people (especially the youths) as jobless and idle individuals tend to involve in ethno religious violence.
- ii. Religious leaders and scholars (Imams and pastors) should be guided to preach tolerance and admonish their followers on the importance of peaceful coexistence with adherent of other faiths.
- iii. Government should partner with NGOs and faith-based organizations to promote peace and harmonious coexistence between people of different creed and identity.
- iv. Government should consider minority groups for appointments; this would give them a sense of inclusion and belonging, thereby reduce frustration and aggression.
- v. Recreational spaces should be reclaimed and new one's earmark to tame the excessive energy of the youth usually misdirected in prosecuting the conflicts.
- vi. Elected officials should be tasked to run an all-inclusive government by bringing everyone on board so that no group would feel left behind or marginalized in running the affairs of the state.

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